

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

**2026-YIL / IYUN/6-SON,
IV-QISM**

INTERNATIONAL
STANDARD
SERIAL
NUMBER
INTERNATIONAL CENTRE

ISSN: 2992-8982

<https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz/>

IQTISODIYOT&TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Bosh muharrir:

Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich

Bosh muharrir o'rinbosari:

Karimov Norboy G'aniyevich

Muharrir:

Qurbonov Sherzod Ismatillayevich

*Elektron nashr. 2026-yil, iyun.
IV-qism*

Tahrir hay'ati:

Salimov Oqil Umrzoqovich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Abduraxmanov Kalandar Xodjayevich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Rae Kvon Chung, Janubiy Koreya, TDIU faxriy professori, "Nobel" mukofoti laureati
Osman Mesten, Turkiya parlamenti a'zosi, Turkiya – O'zbekiston do'stlik jamiyati rahbari
Axmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Axmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Abduraxmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Kalonov Muxiddin Baxritdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Siddiqova Sadoqat G'afforovna, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Xudoyqulov Sadirdin Karimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Maxmudov Nosir, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Samadov Asqarjon Nishonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, professor
Slizovskiy Dimitriy Yegorovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Axmedov Ikrom Akramovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Eshtayev Alisher Abdug'aniyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Xajiyev Baxtiyor Dushaboyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Hakimov Nazar Hakimovich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Musayeva Shoirazimovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), professor
Ali Konak (Ali Ko'nak), iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor (Turkiya)
Cham Tat Huei, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD), professor (Malayziya)
Foziljonov Ibrohimjon Sotvoldix'o'ja o'g'li, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dots.
Faxridinov Zafarjon Faxridin o'g'li, O'zb. Res. Bosh prokuraturasi HIJQKD boshqarma boshlig'i
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, Anijon viloyati prokurorining o'rinbosari
Ochilov Farkhod, O'zb. Res. Bosh prokuraturasi IJQK Departamentining Namangan viloyati boshqarmasi boshlig'i
Buzrukxonov Sarvarxon Munavvarxonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Axmedov Javohir Jamolovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Toxirov Jaloliddin Ochil o'g'li, texnika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), katta o'qituvchi
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), v.b. dots.
Djudi Smetana, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)
Krissi Lyuis, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)
Glazova Marina Viktorovna, Iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (Moskva)
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD) (Turkiya)
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhamatjon o'g'li, TDIU ITI departamenti rahbari
Ochilov Bobur Baxtiyor o'g'li, TDIU katta o'qituvchisi
Golisheva Yelena Vyacheslavovna, Iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent.
Abdukarimova Dinara Rustamxonovna, bank-moliya akademiyasi professori, DSc., professor.
Ikramov Murod Akramovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Nazarova Ra'no Rustamovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Editorial board:

Salimov Okil Umrzokovich, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan
Abdurakhmanov Kalandar Khodjavevich, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Rae Kwon Chung, South Korea, Honorary Professor at TSUE, Nobel Prize Laureate
Osman Mesten, Member of the Turkish Parliament, Head of the Turkey–Uzbekistan Friendship Society
Akhmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Akhmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Abdurakhmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Kalonov Mukhiddin Bakhridinovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Siddikova Sadokat Gafforovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogical Sciences
Khudoykulov Sadirdin Karimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Makhmudov Nosir, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Samadov Askarjon Nishonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Professor
Slizovskiy Dmitriy Yegorovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Akhmedov Ikrom Akramovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Eshtayev Alisher Abduganiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khajiyev Bakhtiyor Dushaboyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khakimov Nazar Khakimovich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Professor
Ali Konak, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor (Turkey)
Cham Tat Huei, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD), Professor (Malaysia)
Foziljonov Ibrokhimjon Sotvoldikhoja ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Fakhridinov Zafarjon Fakhridin ogli, Head of the DCEC under the Prosecutor General's Office of the Rep. of Uzb.
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, Deputy Prosecutor of Anijan Region
Ochilov Farkhod, Head of the Namangan Regional Department of the Department of Internal Affairs of Rep. of Uzb.
Buzrukkhonov Sarvarkhon Munavvarkhonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Akhmedov Javokhir Jamolovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences
Tokhirov Jaloliddin Ochil ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Technical Sciences, Senior Lecturer
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Acting Associate Professor
Judi Smetana, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)
Chrissy Lewis, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)
Glazova Marina Victorovna, Doctor of Sciences in Economics (Moscow)
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin kizi, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) (Turkey)
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhamatjon ugli, Head of the Department of Scientific Research and Innovations, TSUE
Ochilov Bobur Bakhtiyor ugli, Senior lecturer at TSUI
Golisheva Yelena Vyacheslavovna, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor.
Abdukarimova Dinara Rustamkhanovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Ikramov Murod Akramovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Nazarova Ra'no Rustamovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Ekspertlar kengashi:

Berkinov Bazarbay, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Po'latov Baxtiyor Alimovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Aliyev Bekdavlat Aliyevich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Xalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Rustamov Ilhomiddin, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Hakimov Ziyodulla Ahmadovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
G'afurov Doniyor Orifovich, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Tuxtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Xamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarim qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Yaxshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, katta o'qituvchi
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, mustaqil tadqiqotchi
Komilova Nilufar Karshiboyevna, Geografiya fanlari doktori, professori
Umirzoqov Ja'sur Artiqboy o'g'li, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), dotsent
Zebo Kuldasheva, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), dotsent

Board of Experts:

Berkinov Bazarbay, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Pulatov Bakhtiyor Alimovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Aliyev Bekdavlat Aliyevich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Rustamov Ilhomiddin, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Khakimov Ziyodulla Akhmadovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics
Gafurov Doniyor Orifovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogy
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Tukhtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Khamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarimovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Yakhshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, Senior Lecturer
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, Independent Researcher
Komilova Nilufar Karshiboyevna, Doctor of Geographical Sciences, Professor
Umirzokov Jasur Artiqboy ugli, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Associate Professor
Zebo Kuldasheva, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Associate Professor

- 08.00.01 Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.04 Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.05 Xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlari iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.06 Ekonometrika va statistika
- 08.00.07 Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
- 08.00.08 Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
- 08.00.09 Jahon iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.10 Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.11 Marketing
- 08.00.12 Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
- 08.00.13 Menejment
- 08.00.14 Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
- 08.00.15 Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.16 Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
- 08.00.17 Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

Muassis: "Ma'rifat-print-media" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti,
O'zbekiston Respublikasi Bosh prokuraturasi huzuridagi Iqtisodiy
jinoyatlarga qarshi kurashish departamenti

Jurnalning ilmiyligi:

“Yashil” iqtisodiyot va
taraqqiyot” jurnali

O'zbekiston Respublikasi
Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar
vazirligi huzuridagi Oliy
attestatsiya komissiyasi
rayosatining
2023-yil 1-apreldagi
336/3-sonli qarori bilan
ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

MUNDARIJA

YASHIL ENERGIYA SEKTORIDA VENCHUR INVESTITSIYALARINING RIVOJLANISHI: GLOBAL TENDENSIYALAR VA O'ZBEKISTON IMKONIYATLARI	12
Qarajanova Gulnoza Tolliyevna	
MILLIY KOMPANIYALARNI BAYNALMILALLASHUV BOSQICHLARI VA XALQARO KORPORATIV BIRLASHUVLAR (M&A) STRATEGIYASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	19
Shokirov Shoxruxmirzo Baxtiyorjon o'g'li	
QISHLOQ XO'JALIGINI IQLIM VA EKOLOGIK O'ZGARISHLARGA MOSLASHTIRISHDA SMART TEXNOLOGIYALARNI JORIY ETISH METODOLOGIYASINI RIVOJLANTIRISH.....	23
Mirzataev Salamat Muratbaevich	
QISHLOQ XO'JALIGIDA MEVACHILIK KLASSTERLARINI TASHKIL ETISHNING ISHLAB CHIQRISH VA RENTABELLIK KO'RSATKICHLARIGA TA'SIRI	28
Tureev Azizbek Abatovich	
QORAQALPOG'ISTON RESPUBLIKASIDA QURILISH XIZMATLARINI SUN'IY INTELLEKT ASOSIDA RIVOJLANTIRISHNING STRATEGIK MODELII.....	32
Qidirniyazov Ajiniyaz Sherniyazovich	
TOG'-KON SANOATI KORXONALARIDA RESURS TEJAMKOR TEXNOLOGIYALAR ASOSIDA IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIKNI OSHIRISHNING NAZARIY-USLUBIY ASOSLARI.....	37
Kurbanova Mehriniso Nematjanovna	
Sharipov Kongratbay Avezimbetovich	
THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE NATIONAL INSURANCE MARKET AND THE LEVEL OF INCLUSIVENESS.....	43
Ravshanova Mohinur O'rolovna	
O'ZBEKISTON TEMIR YO'LLARI AJ KORXONALARIDA IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIKNI OSHIRISHNING ZAMONAVIY YONDASHUVLARI.....	51
Kurbonova Ma'mura Abdukarim qizi	
TO'QIMACHILIK SANOATI KORXONALARINING MOLIYAVIY BARQARORLIGINI TA'MINLASH MEXANIZMLARI.....	55
Qaraev Anvar Botirovich	
THE IMPACT OF LOYALTY PROGRAMS ON CUSTOMER RETENTION IN ONLINE COSMETICS: A MIXED-METHODS STUDY	61
Toirova Mubina	
IQLIM O'ZGARISHI VA "YASHIL" TRANSFORMATSIYANING JAHON MOLIYA BOZORLARIGA TA'SIRI.....	66
Qo'chqorova Muxlisaxon Ulug'bek qizi	
KICHIK BIZNES RIVOJLANISHIDA RAQAMLI PLATFORMALAR - ELEKTRON TIJORAT SAYTLARI, MARKETPLEYSLAR VA MOBIL ILOVALARNING O'RNI.....	73
Rizayeva Nilufar Oblakulovna	
SUN'IY INTELLEKT TEXNOLOGIYALARINING BIZNES JARAYONLARINI OPTIMALLASHTIRISHDAGI IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIGI	79
Abdulla Mavlonov	
QISHLOQ XO'JALIGIDA SABZAVOTCHILIK MAHSULOTLARI LOGISTIKASINI RAQAMLASHTIRISH ORQALI BOZOR INFRATUZILMASI SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH.....	82
Komekova Gulzira Sharbaevna	

МЕТОДОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ПОДХОДЫ К АГРЕГИРОВАНИЮ РАЗРОЗНЕННЫХ ДАННЫХ В ЭКОНОМЕТРИЧЕСКИХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯХ	87
Бекматов Акмал Курбонмахматович	
SUG'URTA TASHKIOTLARIDA MHXSGA O'TISHNING HOZIRGI HOLATI VA MUAMMOLARI	93
Azamatova G. I.	
O'ZBEKISTON SOG'LIQNI SAQLASH TIZIMINI RAQAMLASHTIRISHGA YO'NALTIRILGAN INVESTITSİYALARNING XARAJAT-FOYDA TAHLILI	98
Omonov Olim Murodullayevich	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA INNOVATSION TA'LIM TEXNOLOGIYALARINI JORIY ETISHNING IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIGI	104
Isxakova Sarvar Ayubovna	
Amriyeva Shaxzoda Shuxratovna	
ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ МЕТОДОВ МАШИННОГО ОБУЧЕНИЯ В КРЕДИТНОМ СКОРИНГЕ РОЗНИЧНЫХ ЗАЁМЩИКОВ: ОПЫТ АКБ «КАПИТАЛБАНК» (РЕСПУБЛИКА УЗБЕКИСТАН)	109
Жанайдарова Камола Абаевна	
INVESTITSION LOYIHALARNI MOLIYALASHTIRISHDA IPO VA KORPORATIV OBLIGATSIYALAR SAMARADORLIGI	115
G'afurov Sherzod Abdvaxob o'g'li	
O'ZBEKISTON TURIZM BOZORINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA MARKETING TADQIQOTLARNING AHAMIYATI	120
Usmanova Zumrad Islamovna	
O'ZBEKISTONDA YASHIL VODOROD IQTISODIYOTINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING BIZNES VA INVESTITSION MEKANIZMLARI	123
Nuraliyeva Komila Sanaqulovna	
XUFYONA IQTISODIYOTNI QISQARTIRISHDA XALQARO TAJRIBALAR TAHLILI: SOLIQ ISLOHOTLARI VA RAQAMLASHTIRISHNING AHAMIYATI	130
Utkirova Jasmina Jasur qizi	
XORIJIY DAVLATLAR AMALIYOTIDA XUSUSIY INVESTITSİYALAR VA AHOLI DAROMADLARI O'RTASIDAGI MUTANOSIBLIKNI TARTIBGA SOLISH YO'NALISHLARI	135
Salimova Zaxro Sobirjon qizi	
QAYTA TIKLANUVCHI ENERGIYA MANBALARINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING IQTISODIY TAHLILI VA BASHORATI	141
Xakimov D.R.	
ВЛИЯНИЕ ТЕХНОЛОГИЧЕСКОГО ПРОГРЕССА НА ЗАНЯТОСТЬ: ОПТИМИЗАЦИЯ И ТРАНСФОРМАЦИЯ РАБОЧИХ МЕСТ	151
Эркинбаева Камила Жавлонбековна	
TIJORAT BANKLARI MOLIYAVIY RESURSLARINI BOSHQARISHNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	156
Tangirkulov Bekzod Boxadirovich	
HUDUDLARDA TURISTLARGA UMUMIY OVQATLANISH XIZMATLARINI KO'RSATISHNING SAMARALI RIVOJLANISH USULLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH: RFEI INDEKSI, KLASSTER MODELI VA "TASTE UZBEKISTAN" RAQAMLI EKOTIZIMI	162
Maxmadiyeva Charos Xayrullayevna	
SAVDODA MARKETING TADQIQOTLARINING ZAMONAVIY TENDENSIYALARI	171
Jalalova Dildora Jamolovna	
КЛИМАТИЧЕСКОЕ ФИНАНСИРОВАНИЕ И ЧЕЛОВЕЧЕСКИЙ КАПИТАЛ В КОНТЕКСТЕ ДОСТИЖЕНИЯ ЦЕЛЕЙ УСТОЙЧИВОГО РАЗВИТИЯ	174
Лана Цхай	
UZOQ MUDDATLI AKTIVLARNI MOLIYAVIY HISOBOTDA AKS ETTIRISHNI MASALALARI	181
G'oziyeva Moxira Rustam qizi	

TA'LIM MUASSASALARIDA LIDERLIK SAMARADORLIGINING NAZARIY-METODOLOGIK ASOSLARI	189
Yuldashova Yoqutoy	
KICHIK VA O'RTA BIZNESNI RAQAMLI KREDITLASHNING O'ZBEKISTON IQTISODIYOTIGA TA'SIRI	193
Karimova Aziza Maxomadrizoyevna Abduraxmonov Faridun Firo'z o'g'li	
SANOAT TARMOQLARIDA QAYTA TIKLANUVCHI ENERGIYA KONSEPSIYASINING IQTISODIY VA INSTITUTSIONAL MAZMUNI	199
Mamarasulova Iroda Zafarjon qizi	
ESG-ТРАНСФОРМАЦИЯ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЙ ПО ПРОИЗВОДСТВУ ПОЛИМЕРНОЙ УПАКОВКИ: ТЕОРИЯ, ОТРАСЛЕВАЯ СПЕЦИФИКА И МИРОВЫЕ ПРАКТИКИ.....	204
Ташпулатов Дильмурад Рустамович	
ENHANCING GREEN ACCOUNTING IN UZBEKISTAN: COMPARATIVE LESSONS FROM DEVELOPED ECONOMIES FOR SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT	210
Xolmurodova Durdona Otamurod qizi	
ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКИЕ, СОЦИАЛЬНЫЕ И ЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ АСПЕКТЫ РАЗВИТИЯ КУЛЬТУРНОГО ТУРИЗМА В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ	218
Саттарова Зухра Илхомовна	
KICHIK BIZNES RIVOJLANISHINING HUDUDIY INVESTITSIYA FAOLLIGIGA TA'SIRI	224
Toirjonov Sardorbek Dilshodjon o'g'li	
HUDUDIY IQTISODIY RIVOJLANISHDA KICHIK BIZNESNING BANDLIKNI TA'MINLASHDAGI AHAMIYATI	229
Mamadaliyev Doniyorbek Shuhratbek o'g'li	
TOSHKENTDA KICHIK BIZNES KORXONALARIDA RAQAMLI TEKNOLOGIYALARDAN FOYDALANISH SAMARADORLIGI: LOGIT VA PROBIT MODELLARI ASOSIDA EMPIRIK TAHLIL	235
Hasan Ibragimov Mannonov Shahzod Toshmurod Qulmanov	
MOSLASHUVCHAN MENEJMENT VA UNING SIFAT BOSHQARUVIDAGI O'RNI	242
Ibroximova Zuhra Baxtiyor qizi	
IJTIMOIIY SOHANI BARQAROR RIVOJLANTIRISHNING MINTAQAVIY XUSUSIYATLARI	247
Ro'zmetov Kamol Ibodullayevich Ibragimov Qayumbek Ikromovich	
TIJORAT BANKLARI AKTIVLARI SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHNING ILG'OR XORIY TAJRIBALARI	254
Muminov Bekzod Polvonovich	
KORPORATIV AXBOROT TIZIMLARINI RAQAMLASHTIRISH KONSEPSIYASINING NAZARIY EVOLYUTSIYASI VA ZAMONAVIY YONDASHUVLAR TASNIFI.....	263
Kuchkarov Ulug'bek Tahirovich	
O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI MINTAQALARIDA EKSPORT FAOLIYATINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING NAZARIY-METODOLOGIK ASOSLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	268
Abdulatifova Moxinur Alisher qizi	
FIZIKA FANINI SUN'IY INTELLEKT INTEGRATSIYASI ASOSIDA SAMARALI O'QITISHNING INNOVATSION YONDASHUVLARI.....	275
Razzoqov I.D.	
RAQAMLI MEHNAT BOZORLARI VA IQTISODIY BARQARORLIK: O'ZBEKISTON VA QOZOG'ISTON MISOLIDA QIYOSIY TAHLIL	281
Safarova Gulruh Akmal qizi	
СОЦИАЛЬНО-ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКАЯ СУЩНОСТЬ КАТЕГОРИИ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ И НАУЧНЫЙ	

ПОДХОД К ЕЁ ОПРЕДЕЛЕНИЮ.....	287
Зайналов Ж. Р.	
О'ZBEKISTONDA KICHIK BIZNES SUBYEKTLARINING MAMLAKAT IQTISODIYOTIDAGI O'RNI.....	293
Xolmatova Mumtozbeqim Alisherxon qizi	
TURISTIK BOZOR KONYUNKTURASINI O'RGANISHNING NAZARIY VA AMALIY JIHATLARI.....	298
Usmanova Zumrad Islamovna	
PREPARATION OF NUT JAM USING MULBERRY SYRUP BASED ON ITS CONSUMER PROPERTIES.....	302
Pardaev Gayrat Yakhshibaevich	

PREPARATION OF NUT JAM USING MULBERRY SYRUP BASED ON ITS CONSUMER PROPERTIES

Pardaev Gayrat Yakhshibaevich
Senior Lecturer, Marketing Department
Samarkand Institute of Economics and Service
Email: gpardaev2018@mail.ru
ORCID: 0000-0003-0181-6530

Abstract: This paper explores the potential of using mulberry syrup, made from mulberry fruits that ripen almost simultaneously with walnuts in the milky stage, as an alternative to sugar in the preparation of walnut jam. A comparative analysis of the consumer properties, including organoleptic, physicochemical, and other characteristics, was conducted for products with added sugar and those with mulberry syrup. The results showed that mulberry syrup not only improves the taste and aroma of the product but also enhances its functional properties due to its content of biologically active substances. We also consider the organoleptic characteristics of this jam, which are directly related to consumer properties. The antioxidant properties of this jam were also characterized. Furthermore, this article reflects the government's interest in the development of walnuts, in connection with the creation of a walnut growing association, as the nut is an export-oriented commodity in some countries and is in high demand worldwide. This article also discusses the historical significance of this product in the life of our region.

Keywords: Walnut; Consumer properties; Mulberry syrup; Jam; Sugar; Organoleptic evaluation.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola yong'och murabboni tayyorlashda shakarga alternativa sifatida sutli bosqichdagi yong'och bilan deyarli bir vaqtning o'zida pishadigan tut mevalaridan tayyorlangan tut siropidan foydalanish imkoniyatlarini o'rganadi. Shakar qo'shilgan va tut siropi qo'shilgan mahsulotlar uchun iste'mol xususiyatlarining, jumladan, organoleptik, fizik-kimyoviy va boshqa xususiyatlarning qiyosiy tahlili o'tkazildi. Natijalar shuni ko'rsatdiki, tut siropi nafaqat mahsulotning ta'mi va xushbo'yiligini yaxshilaydi, balki biologik faol moddalar miqdori tufayli uning funksional xususiyatlarini ham oshiradi. Shuningdek, ushbu murabboning iste'mol xususiyatlari bilan bevosita bog'liq bo'lgan organoleptik xususiyatlari ham ko'rib chiqiladi. Ushbu murabboning antioksidant xususiyatlari ham tavsiflangan. Bundan tashqari, ushbu maqola yong'och yetishtiruvchilar assotsiatsiyasini yaratish munosabati bilan hukumatning yong'ochchilikni rivojlantirishga qiziqishini aks ettiradi, chunki yong'och ayrim mamlakatlarda eksportga yo'naltirilgan tovar hisoblanadi va butun dunyo bo'ylab yuqori talabga ega. Ushbu maqolada, shuningdek, mazkur mahsulotning mintaqamiz hayotidagi tarixiy ahamiyati muhokama qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: yong'och, iste'mol xususiyatlari, tut siropi, murabbo, shakar, organoleptik baholash.

Аннотация: В данной статье исследуется потенциал использования сиропа из шелковицы, приготовленного из плодов шелковицы, созревающих почти одновременно с грецкими орехами в молочной стадии, в качестве альтернативы сахару при приготовлении орехового джема. Проведен сравнительный анализ потребительских свойств, включая органолептические, физико-химические и другие характеристики, продуктов с добавлением сахара и продуктов с сиропом из шелковицы. Результаты показали, что сироп из шелковицы не только улучшает вкус и аромат продукта, но и повышает его функциональные свойства благодаря содержанию биологически активных веществ. Также рассмотрены органолептические характеристики этого джема, которые напрямую связаны с потребительскими свойствами. Были также охарактеризованы антиоксидантные свойства этого джема. Кроме того, в статье отражен интерес правительства к развитию выращивания грецких орехов в связи с созданием ассоциации грецких ореховодов, поскольку этот орех является экспортно-ориентированным товаром в некоторых странах и пользуется высоким спросом во всем мире. В статье также обсуждается историческое значение этого продукта в жизни нашего региона.

Ключевые слова: Грецкий орех; Свойства для потребителей; Шелковичный сироп; Джем; Сахар; Органолептическая оценка.

INTRODUCTION

Uzbekistan is renowned for its diverse agricultural crops, among which nuts hold a special place. The history of nut cultivation in Uzbekistan dates back to ancient times. Archaeological finds indicate that the ancient civilizations that inhabited this land already valued these crops. Currently, special attention is being paid to the development of nut production, particularly walnuts. This is evidenced by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated June 1, 2017, "On the Establishment and Organization of the Activities of the Association of Walnut Producers and Exporters" (President's Decree No. PP-3025, 2017). This Decree provides for the efficient use of rainfed lands and an increase in walnut production to make it competitive in both domestic and foreign markets. Through the creation of modern plantations and the active implementation of scientifically based methods, intensive technologies for growing and processing walnut fruits based on attracting foreign investment, researchers have recently carried out significant work on the study of genetic resources, biochemical properties, as well as selection and propagation of walnuts (Vahdati et al., 2019).

Walnuts (*Juglans regia* L.) are valued for their nutritional and health benefits, especially at the milk-ripe stage. Sugar is traditionally used to make jam, but with the growing interest in healthy eating, the search for natural syrups as sweeteners is relevant (Akpinar-Bayazit, 2010). Mulberry syrup, obtained from mulberry fruits, has high nutritional value and can serve as a worthy alternative to sugar (Kang et al., 2016). This sweetener is rich in B vitamins, iron, potassium, and amino acids (Gursoy & Sarikurcu, 2019).

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

Existing research highlights the nutritional and technological potential of both walnuts and mulberry-based products. Akpinar-Bayazit demonstrated the high nutritional value of black mulberry (*Morus nigra* L.) in her research, highlighting its content of bioactive compounds. Y. Kang further confirmed the antioxidant and anti-inflammatory activity of green walnut shell extracts in their article, substantiating the feasibility of using walnuts in functional foods. N. Gursoy and S. Sarikürkçü presented a comprehensive review of *Morus* species, demonstrating that mulberry syrup is rich in B vitamins, iron, potassium, and essential amino acids, making it a functional ingredient rather than just a sweetener.

From a technological perspective, replacing refined sugar with natural syrups is a growing trend in food science. Livesey G. discussed the health potential of sugar substitutes, particularly their low-glycemic properties, which is especially important for diabetics and health-conscious consumers. Molyneux P. standardized the DPPH method for assessing antioxidant activity, a method widely used to compare the free radical scavenging capacity of fruit products. In the context of Uzbekistan, the strategic importance of walnut cultivation was officially recognized by Presidential Decree No. PP-3025 of Mirziyoyev Sh.M., which encourages the implementation of modern, intensive technologies and scientific methods. Furthermore, Vahdati K., Arab M.M., Sarikhani S., Sadat Hosseini M., Leslie C.A., and Brown P.J. reviewed global advances in walnut breeding strategies, including genetic resource management and breeding methods, which are directly related to improving the quality of raw materials for processing. However, despite the recognized benefits of mulberry syrup and the nutritional value of walnuts, no systematic studies have previously been conducted on the feasibility of replacing sugar syrup with mulberry syrup in the production of jam from unripe walnuts. Specifically, the impact of such a substitution on organoleptic properties, pH, antioxidant activity, and microbiological stability remains unexplored. All of these qualities influence the consumer properties of jams made from unripe walnuts, which in turn enhances their consumer appeal. This gap in the literature justifies the present study.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Our research methods included assessing the quality of the control and experimental samples and evaluating them organoleptically based on taste, aroma, color, and texture. To enhance the reliability of the organoleptic method, we conducted tasting evaluations on a 5-point scale. Eleven tasters participated in the tasting. The tasters processed the results statistically, calculating the arithmetic mean of each indicator on a 5-point scale. We also determined dry matter content using refractometry, pH using a digital pH meter, and total antioxidant activity using the DRRN method.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The main objective of this study was to examine the possibility of replacing sugar syrup with a natural product, mulberry syrup, when making jam from milk-ripe walnuts. Mulberry syrup, due to its significant vitamin and micronutrient content, enriches the finished product with these valuable biologically active substances.

On the other hand, mulberry syrup contains easily digestible sugars—glucose and fructose—which are also present in this jam and can be recommended for diabetics.

We prepared two batches of jam:

- 1) Control—based on 1 kg of milk-ripe walnuts with the addition of 0.5 kg of a 60% sugar syrup solution;
- 2) Experimental—based on 1 kg of milk-ripe walnuts with the sugar syrup replaced by 0.5 kg of mulberry syrup with a soluble solids concentration of 12%. As is well known, walnuts at the milky stage have a bitter taste due to their high tannins and organic acids. To remove this bitterness, the nuts were thinly peeled, pierced, and soaked in water for 5 days, changing the water daily. To completely remove the bitterness, they were then soaked again in a 5% lime solution. Following this, both samples were boiled in three 30-minute increments over medium heat, with 25-30 minute rests in between, following the recipe described above. The control samples were boiled to a soluble solids content of 62%, and the test samples to a soluble solids content of 58%. The resulting control and test jam samples were then subjected to quality testing for organoleptic and physicochemical properties.

The results of the comparative 5-point quality assessment of the control and test jam samples are presented in Table 1 (Table 1).

Table 1
Results of organoleptic evaluation of jam quality¹

Samples	Indicators on a 5-point scale				Average score
	Vux	Aroma	Consistency	Color	
Control sample	4,1	3,9	4,5	3,8	4,07
Prototype	4,7	4,8	4,6	4,9	4,76

As can be seen from Table 1, walnut jam made with milk-ripe walnuts and natural mulberry syrup, replacing sugar syrup, improves the organoleptic properties of the finished product, as the average score for the test sample was 4.76, while the control sample scored 4.07.

For fruit jam, pH is an important parameter. According to our studies, the pH of the control samples was 4.2, while that of the test sample was 4.5. Thus, the addition of natural mulberry syrup shifts the pH toward an alkaline equilibrium.

Antioxidant activity was significantly higher in the batch with mulberry syrup (26.1 mg/g versus 18.4 mg/g) based on ascorbic acid equivalents (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Antioxidant activity² (mg/g)

¹ Source: Developed by the author.

² Source: Developed by the author.

After 30 days of storage at 40°C, none of the batches showed signs of microbiological spoilage. Mulberry syrup improves the flavor, aroma, and nutritional value of unripe walnut jam. The results indicate that mulberry syrup can be used as a substitute for sugar syrup when making jam from unripe walnuts. The main advantages of using mulberry syrup include:

- improved organoleptic characteristics due to fruity notes and mild caramelization;
- increased antioxidant activity of the product, which is important for functional nutrition (Gursoy, N, 2019; Molyneux, P, 2004);

- reduced glycemic load, especially important for consumers with limited sugar intake (Livesey, G, 2003).

It has also been noted that mulberry syrup is able to preserve the structural integrity of the nuts, preventing their tissue breakdown during cooking, which may be due to its gentle composition and acidity.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

The use of mulberry syrup in the preparation of unripe walnut jam enhances the product's nutritional and consumer value and improves its organoleptic properties. The obtained data confirm the potential of mulberry syrup as a natural sugar substitute in the food industry, particularly within the context of the trend toward functional and healthy foods.

REFERENCES:

1. Akpinar-Bayazit, A., et al. (2010). Nutritive value of black mulberry (*Morus nigra* L.). *Pakistan Journal of Nutrition*, 9(3), 264–269.
2. Gursoy, N., & Sarikurkcu, C. (2019). Nutritional composition and biological properties of *Morus* species: a review. *Journal of Functional Foods*, 60, 103-415.
3. Kang, Y. R., et al. (2016). Antioxidant and anti-inflammatory activities of walnut green husk extract. *Food Science and Biotechnology*, 25(3), 945–953.
4. Livesey, G. (2003). Health potential of polyols as sugar replacers, with emphasis on low glycemic properties. *Nutrition Research Reviews*, 16(2), 163–191.
5. Molyneux, P. (2004). The use of the stable free radical DPPH for estimating antioxidant activity. *Songklanakarin Journal of Science and Technology*, 26(2), 211–219.
6. Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated June 1, 2017, № RP-3025 “On the establishment and organization of activities of the association of walnut producers and exporters” // URL: <https://lex.uz/ru/docs/7491755>
7. Vahdati K, Arab MM, Sarikhani S, Sadat Hosseini M, Leslie CA, Brown PJ (2019) Advances in walnut (*Juglans regia* L.) breeding strategies. In: JM Al-Khayri, SM Jain and DV Johnson (eds.) *Advances in plant breeding strategies*, Vol 4. Nut and Beverage Crops. Springer, Switzerland.

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz HAKIMOV

Musahhih: Zokir ALIBEKOV

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Hasan MAQSUDOV

2026. № 6/4

© Materiallar ko'chirib bosilganda "Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali manba sifatida ko'rsatilishi shart. Jurnalda bosilgan material va reklamalardagi dalillarning aniqligiga mualliflar ma'sul. Tahririyat fikri har vaqt ham mualliflar fikriga mos kelmasligi mumkin. Tahririyatga yuborilgan materiallar qaytarilmaydi.

Mazkur jurnalda maqolalar chop etish uchun quyidagi havolalarga maqola, reklama, hikoya va boshqa ijodiy materiallar yuborishingiz mumkin. Materiallar va reklamalar pullik asosda chop etiladi.

EI.Pochta: sq143235@gmail.com

Bot: @iqtisodiyot_77

Tel.: 93 718 40 07

Jurnalga istalgan payt quyidagi rekvizitlar orqali obuna bo'lishingiz mumkin. Obuna bo'lgach, @iqtisodiyot_77 telegram sahifamizga to'lov haqidagi ma'lumotni skrinshot yoki foto shaklida jo'natishingizni so'raymiz. Shu asosda har oygi jurnal yangi sonini manzilingizga jo'natamiz.

"Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali 03.11.2022-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №566955 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug'bek tumani
Kumushkon ko'chasi, 26-uy.

Jurnal sayti: <https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz>